

EFFECTIVENESS OF PROPER NUTRITION IN PREVENTING DIABETES MELLITUS

Polvanova G.U.

Urgench branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy

Currently, hereditary predisposition to diabetes mellitus has been proven, and the pathogenetic basis of diabetes depends on the type of disease, and two fundamentally different types are distinguished. Although modern endocrinology calls the classification of the disease conditional, it is important to determine the treatment strategy for each of its types.

The most important basis of the problem is the disruption of the interaction of insulin with tissues. Glucose is necessary for the body as the main energy substrate for maintaining vital processes. The inability of glucose to penetrate into tissues and its inability to be stored in the liver in the form of glycogen leads to an increase in its level in the blood.

There are two main links in the pathogenesis of diabetes:

1. Insufficient production of insulin by endocrine cells of the pancreas.
2. Violation of the interaction of insulin with the cells of the body's tissues (insulin resistance).

As mentioned above, diabetes can be transmitted from parents to children. If one of the parents has this disease, the probability of passing it on to offspring is 10% for type 1 and 80% for type 2.

Insulin is not always necessary to treat the disease. Only a qualified doctor can determine the treatment regimen.

First of all, such patients are prescribed a diet. It is important to follow the doctor's recommendations. It is recommended to gradually lose weight, 2-3 kg per month, until the body weight returns to normal. If the diet is not followed, drugs are prescribed to reduce blood sugar levels, and in the most severe cases - insulin.

The main tasks of the doctor in the treatment of diabetes are:

Compensation of carbohydrate metabolism;

Prevention and treatment of complications;

Normalization of body weight;

Ensure patient understanding.

Compensation of carbohydrate metabolism is achieved in two ways:

Providing cells with insulin is carried out in different ways depending on the type of diabetes.

Maintaining a constant carbohydrate intake through diet.

Patient education is very important in diabetes treatment. The patient should have a clear understanding of what the disease is, its risks, what to do during hypo- and hyperglycemia episodes, how to avoid them, how to independently monitor blood glucose levels, as well as the permitted diet.

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Diet for diabetes is as important a part of therapy as taking insulin or drugs that lower blood sugar. Compensation of carbohydrate metabolism without diet is impossible.

It is worth noting that in some cases of type 2 diabetes, diet alone is enough to compensate for carbohydrate metabolism, especially in the early stages. In type 1 diabetes, diet is critical, and failure to comply with it can lead to hypo- or hyperglycemic coma, and in some cases, to the death of the patient.

The diet should be balanced in terms of carbohydrates, fats and proteins. Easily digestible carbohydrates should be completely excluded from the diet.

The basic concept in diet therapy is the bread unit. This is a conventional unit equal to 10-12 g of carbohydrates or 20-25 g of bread. The number of bread units consumed by the patient during the day should remain unchanged. Depending on body weight and physical activity, this is on average 12-25 units.

It is not recommended to consume more than 7 bread units of carbohydrates at a time. It is recommended to organize the meal schedule so that the daily amount of food is the same at each meal. It should be noted that alcohol consumption can lead to prolonged hypoglycemia, in particular, hypoglycemic coma.

Another important aspect is keeping a food diary by the patient. All products consumed during the day are recorded in it. Based on this, the number of bread units consumed per meal and per day is calculated. It also helps to determine the cause of hypo- and hyperglycemia episodes.

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